

University of Reading

Planning adaptation of Artificial Islands for climate change: A sustainable approach for urban expansion - Case studies from Denmark

An analysis of Lynetteholm and Holmene development of their planning, risk responses, and emerging opportunities in Denmark's urban expansion.

by

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Abstract

Climate extremes across the world are growing and posing risks to the coastal regions as it is vital economic hubs, serving as gateways to trade and settlement. Denmark, a country with little elevation and its capital Copenhagen facing risks from sea level rise and flooding with the government's commitment to tackling them. One of the factors which adds to this absence of progress is that the sea level rise is exceeding the infrastructure capability planning ahead for climate adaptation with projections of changing coastal landscape. Without a framework that could assess and respond to risk factors of the existing coastal development and limits the climate adaptation implementation, contributing to the retreat of communities and damage to economic vulnerability. The research undertaken within the study includes case studies of Lynetteholm, an artificial island and seaward development extension and Holmene, nine artificial islands and seaward development extension. Both case studies are located on the coast of Copenhagen, Denmark. Their strategic objectives are to be new frontiers that are facing climate extremes and facilitating development. This study by focusing on planning practice offers modern and innovative practical implications to mitigate the risks while open for emerging opportunities and a brand-new theoretical framework, the 'Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension'. Conceptual justification for this approach is Denmark's planning system and document analysis of Lynetteholm and Holmene planning process with other risk factor models, while practical implications for the 'Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension' in action are assessed through urgency of the city expansion according to the risks and opportunity provided long term vision and monitoring process of adjustment to the framework.

Keywords: Artificial Island, Climate Adaptation, Climate Extreme, Coastal Landscape, Seaward Development, Maritime Urban Planning, Sea Level Rise, Urban Extension.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Problem Statement, Urgency, and Environment

In 2018, the Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change stated that the effects of climate change are irreversible. The rising sea level affects two of five people who live within 100 kilometres of the coast and leaves 90 per cent of megacities worldwide vulnerable. Later, in New York, in April 2022 – the United Nations Headquarters has announced that the efforts toward climate proof infrastructure investment in addressing rising sea level might be ineffective as the climate extreme accelerate exceeded the infrastructure capability built. Climate adaptation solutions become the baseline to addressing the sea level rise, as the UN assembly introduced the prototype of sustainable artificial islands by UN-Habitat, Oceanix, and the Busan Metropolitan City of the Republic of Korea. Showcase the vision of potential seaward settlements to facilitate life on water, as the urbanism movement. This movement has made implementation in Copenhagen, Denmark. In the Lynetteholm and Holmene project in addressing the climate and economic challenges through artificial island and seaward urban extension.

The world's coastal regions have long been recognised as vital economic hubs, serving as gateways to global trade and settlement for most of the human population. Due to climate change extreme, the recent generalised sea level and temperature rise increase in frequency and intensity of storms and extreme temperatures impacted coastal communities and development of coastal flooding and erosion (Laino and Igesias, 2023). Even more alarming, in the recent three months from October 2023 to January 2024, Denmark has faced 20 years-recorded snowdrifts with rainfall, repeated and flash flooding damage the city of Copenhagen and Southeast region of Denmark (Hivert, 2024).

“Unfortunately, we have to prepare for more severe weather events like these in the future, especially with more water” warned Danish Environment Minister Magnus Johannes Heunicke on 5th January 2024 and highlighting the “importance of accelerating coastal protection and climate adaptation.” After occurrence of repeated flooding and high tide in Southeast region of Denmark. This quoted bring the importance to this dissertation about the planning adaptation needed for the future urban’s growth.

The Lynetteholm & Holmene, key case studies of this dissertation for seaward urban extension occur for several drivers. With urban agglomeration presenting challenges and a population of around 5.9 million, Denmark stands as the most densely populated country in the Nordic Region. Approximately 1.3 million individuals reside in and around the capital city, Copenhagen (Nordic Co-operation, 2023). Given the limited space available in Copenhagen, the Danish Government faces the dual challenge of land scarcity and rising sea levels in the surrounding areas. The geological landscape, comprising the Jutland peninsula and 78 inhabited islands out of a total of 1419 islands (Statistics Denmark, 2024), necessitates unique and distinctive approaches to Danish land reclamation projects. One such method involves the creation of artificial islands that extend over the existing coastal landscape.

1.2. Objectives and Aims

This study argues that one limiting factor hindering advancement is the absence of a conceptual model addressing coastal adaptation to climate change in the planning practices of artificial islands and seaward development for urban extension. To test the validity of these claims, this study critically reviews the models used in addressing coastal adaptation to climate change in urban development from planning, economic, and environmental perspectives. These frameworks include the Cost-benefit analysis framework of adaptation planning strategies (Gao and Zhai, 2023), the conceptual framework of coastal vulnerability assessment (Eggert et al., 2023), and a flow chart showing possible driving forces (Sengupta et al., 2018), utilized by analysts and policymakers to determine coastal land reclamation projects. While theoretically, these models provide a conceptual framework to identify planning, risk responses, and emerging opportunities in each development project.

As progress in the field of planning adaptation for seaward development necessitates a model capable of responding swiftly to changes in climate, economics, and politics, there is a need for a more comprehensive understanding. The objective of this study is to develop a planning adaptation model that aligns the long-term seaward development and adjusts to its needs according to situational and contextual propositions. This could study to increase understanding allows for a better approach to addressing the challenges and opportunities presented by seaward urban extension. This study aims to address three challenges from responsiveness, evaluation adaptation, policy direction, and collaborative decision making to illustrated a more comprehensive way to implementing seaward urban extension.

Introducing a new interpretation of risks and opportunities directly impacting seaward development, the 'Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension' model aims to provide theoretical justification for this approach by highlighting the connection between addressing coastal changes and planning for adaptation. This model seeks to promote practical implications in responsive planning and risk management around projects. Through case studies of Lynetteholm and Holmene development, which are discussed in light of their situational and contextual propositions in planning for responsive adaptation to risks such as sea level rise and flooding, the effectiveness of the model can be evaluated. Utilizing documentation analysis as the methodology, developing the model from practical implementations gleaned from existing case studies allows for more effective analysis and evaluation.

1.3. Structure of the Dissertation

'Maritime urban planning for seaward development as climate adaptation, a sustainable exit for urban expansion: the case studies from Denmark.' investigates whether planning practice and the 'Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension' framework can assess the urgency for urban expansion by outweigh risks and opportunities early on for the necessity of development with adequate monitoring and reporting system during the processes. Following this introduction, Chapter 2 begins by forming the foundation of sustainable urban frameworks for coastal adaptation to climate change, Denmark's political and planning system, land reclamation, and strategic development plan. Chapter 3 provides document analysis and methodology to elaborate the case studies of Lynetteholm and Holmene development plan in objective translation linguistically and intentionally into framework. Chapter 4 investigate whether the existing planning implications use to address the artificial islands and seaward development is adequately considering risks and opportunity appropriate to required time and resources. Chapter 5 weighting the various perspective from public engagement, political standpoint, economic and environment viability of the case studies into the 'Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension' framework. Chapter 6 seeks evaluate whether the developed framework theoretically address risks and opportunities for decision-making in maritime urban planning for seaward development with monitoring and reporting process.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Sustainable Urban Frameworks for Coastal Adaptation to Climate Change.

In response to the changing coastal landscape, cities are undertaking land reclamation efforts, which vary depending on the unique locational and situational contexts of each development. Faced with rising sea levels and limited space for urban expansion, land reclamation has become a common practice involving the extraction of sand through drilling and dredging from nearby coastal areas or riverbeds. It is worth noting that annually, the extraction of 50 billion tons of sand for industrial-scale purposes poses a threat to freshwater and coastal ecosystems (Global Centre for Adaptation [GCA], 2022).

The driving forces model (Figure 1) has provided a conceptual framework for understanding the driving factors behind land reclamation. Seaward land expansion resulting from coastal land reclamation is influenced by various factors, encompassing both geophysical and anthropogenic elements that contribute to these projects (Sengupta et al., 2018). These driving forces are applicable to projects such as Lynetteholm and Holmene development, which involve land reclamation to extend Copenhagen's coastline through the creation of artificial islands and seaward development.

Figure 1: Driving Forces for Seaward Urban Extension and Land Reclamation

The construction of artificial shorelines has rapidly increased in coastal cities, particularly those experiencing alterations due to various factors such as waves, currents, storms, changing sea levels, and human interventions in coastal processes, which are closely intertwined with anthropogenic utilization (Smith et al., 2015). However, by using the driving forces model, it overlooked the complexity and the layers of interaction between each factor driven by natural and human activities leading into the oversimplified version of factors that results in land extension. In order to use, driving forces is a specified-time based model which has limited in explore each driver in a linear time direction. For a development using this model means they are condensed their driver factors to a situational and contextual to a specific time. This in turns illustrated

that to effectively address the drives of land extension required to explain the interaction essential for decision-making.

Figure 2: The conceptual framework of coastal vulnerability assessment (Adapted from Eggert et al., 2023). SUD: Sustainable Urban Development, CACC: Coastal Adaptation to Climate Change.

Fig. 2. Part A illustrates the methodological steps used in assessing coastal vulnerability, including collecting, selecting, structuring, and extracting indicators, leading to the consolidation of a comparative analysis of frameworks. Parts B and C detail the sub-steps of the structuring and extraction process. Assessing the vulnerability of coastal sites is crucial for indicating sustainable urban development and adapting to climate change (Eggert et al., 2023). This model is important for the screening processes to do the criteria based into developing context for comprehensive understanding of the development site.

The conceptual framework of coastal vulnerability assessment illustrated a clear and structured approach to collecting and screening indicator sets and frameworks. However, the eligibility criteria used for selecting indicator sets and frameworks may not fully capture the complexity of coastal vulnerability. While criteria such as accessibility, focus on sustainability/coastal adaptation, and city scale are relevant, they may overlook critical factors specific to certain contexts or regions.

Figure 3: The cost-benefit analysis framework of adaptation planning strategies (Gao and Zhai, 2023). SLR: Sea Level Rise, PVNB: Present Value of Net Benefits, CEA: Cost Effective Analysis.

From the Fig 3. Perspective of urban planning, the analysis focuses on planning strategies concerning the accommodation and protection of infrastructures. Four planning strategies with specific scenarios are developed, alongside three methods for calculating benefits. These methods encompass not only direct impacts like land price and property value loss but also indirect socioeconomic impacts such as job opportunities loss and increased travel time (Gao and Zhai, 2023).

Ultimately, the results serve to support decision-makers in adopting and implementing effective strategies. However, in the face of deep uncertainty and changing environmental conditions, adaptive management approaches that emphasize flexibility, learning, and iterative decision-making may be more suitable. This approach allows decision-makers to continuously monitor the effectiveness of adaptation measures, adjust strategies in response to new information, and build resilience to unexpected changes. This is important in the term of planning in Denmark, as its extensive and long-term processes. By considering various pattern, impact, and time into the model. It could response to change and recover from climate change and sea level rise.

2.2. Denmark Planning System, Politics, and Public Engagement

Figure 4: Organisation of spatial and land-use planning in Denmark (OECD, 2017).

The Denmark Planning System play a pivotal role in decision making for the implementation for sustainable development and coastal adaptation the climate change. The planning system in Denmark operates across three levels of government: national, regional, and local (OECD, 2017). The national government, represented by the Ministry for Business and Growth, prepares a national planning report after each parliamentary election. This report provides long-term considerations for spatial development and issues overall guidelines for planning.

The types of construction along the coastline of Denmark are categorized into three distinctive geomorphic models based on their physical appearance. These categories are identified as follows: (1) expanded land construction, involving the extension of artificial land from the existing land surface; (2) offshore construction, where new land is created leaving open water between the coastline and the artificial land; (3) merged construction, in which individual separated landmasses are fused together by landfill. These patterns are observable in the expansion of cities outlined in the Denmark Five-Finger Plan (see

Figure 5). And actively use in the upcoming case studies of seaward urban extension of Lynetteholm and Holmene development.

Figure 5: Earth Observation Images over Copenhagen's Five-Finger Plan
 June 1, 1985 Landsat 5 (path/row 194/21) (left) and June 17, 2014, Landsat 8 (path/row 194/21) (right) – Copenhagen's Five-Finger Plan (Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center – Earthshots, 2014).

Figure 6: A regional growth model. Note: The growth driver 'Welfare service' has in recent applications of the concept been replaced by the original 'Technology-driver'. In the concept applied in this article the technological aspects are embedded in 'Innovation'

Regional governments focus on strategic development planning and formulate Regional Growth and Development Strategies, while municipalities undertake extensive land-use planning, creating municipal and local plans. Denmark's planning framework comprises strategic plans and land-use plans. Strategic plans address national, regional, and municipal strategies, while land-use plans detail regulations for specific development projects (Cornett, 2009). This highlights the correlation between the planning system and Denmark's Strategic Plan, promoting innovation and entrepreneurship across the national level.

Table 1: Functions and units in a system of innovation: Danish example (Cornett, 2009).

	Administration: Policy and financial bodies	Implementation: Tools and programmes	Knowledge institutions: Research and graduate education
Local/regional	Regions (until 2007 counties) and municipalities	Previously TIC, now part of the municipality-based business service system	Universities and R&D institutes. Each region has at least one university. University colleges
National	Ministries and Governmental agencies	GTS (approved technology service institutes) Technological Institutes Consultants	Universities and R&D institutions. Due to mergers in the sector the number of universities and independent R&D institutions reduced significantly in 2006–2007. University colleges.
Spatial/supranational	EU International Agencies	6th and 7th framework programme The Northern Dimension Working Group on Innovation (www.ndinno.net)	Universities and R&D institutes, University colleges

Leading to the involvement in coastal zone management, Denmark using sectoral plans to create integration to the practical implications such as the Water Resources Plan and Natura 2000 Plan outline environmental conditions and objectives. The Five Finger Plan, a National Planning Directive for greater Copenhagen, guides urban development in the metropolitan area (Olesen, 2022). Bringing in major laws and regulations governing planning include the Planning Act, Building Act, Nature Protection Act, and Land Registration Act.

Table 2: The evolution of the Finger Plan doctrine (Olesen, 2022).

Year	Prepared by	Legal status	Principle of spatial organization
1947	Regional Planning Office	Draft, private enterprise	Urban development in palm and fingers The web as green areas Public transport as the backbone of urban corridors
1960	Regional Planning Secretariat	Draft, not approved	Introducing the principle of new towns
1973	Regional Planning Council	Regional plan, approved at metropolitan level	Introducing the principle of decentral urban nodes
1989	Greater Copenhagen Council	Regional plan, approved at metropolitan level	Return to the original principles 'Better city, not more city' Introducing the principle of station proximity
2001	Greater Copenhagen Authority	Regional plan, approved at metropolitan level	The original principles Weak political body
2005	Greater Copenhagen Authority	Regional plan, approved at metropolitan level	The original principles Weak political body
2007	Ministry of the Environment	National planning directive, approved at national level	Strengthening of the original principles
2013	Ministry of the Environment	National planning directive, approved at national level	Focus on the green areas and climate adaptation
2017/2019	Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs	National planning directive, approved at national level	Deregulation - adjustment of the original principles

Figure 7: Central powers in the Danish coastal zone. The legal and regulatory framework establishes a management barrier in the shoreline. CC: County Councils; CD: Coastal Directorate; EA: Energy Agency; EPA: Environment Protection Agency; MC: Municipal councils; MFAF: Ministry for Food, Agriculture & Fisheries; MOE: Ministry of the Environment; MOT: Ministry of Transport; NFA: National Forest & Nature Agency; RCA: Regional Conservation Authorities; SPD: Spatial Planning Department (Anker et al., 2004).

Co-ordination mechanisms ensure alignment between different planning levels, with vertical co-ordination requiring lower-level plans to adhere to higher level directives, and horizontal co-ordination promoting comprehensive consideration of themes and policy sectors (Anker et al., 2004). Expropriations for infrastructure construction are permitted under strict conditions, with compensation provided to landowners. A significant reform in 2007 shifted primary responsibility for land-use planning to municipalities following the amalgamation of local governments. This is relevant to the seaward coastal extension that position as national project because of its scale and its impact to the wider region.

2.3. Coastal Cities, Land Reclamation, and Artificial Island

Urban planners and professionals play a crucial role in addressing climate adaptation, particularly in responding to extreme weather events such as the one witnessed in Copenhagen on July 2, 2011. During this event, Copenhagen endured an unprecedented rainfall, exceeding a 2000-year return period. The repercussions were severe, resulting in significant pluvial flooding and extensive damage to private homes, businesses, public buildings, and infrastructure, including roads and train systems. Insurance claims arising from this event totalled more than 800 million EUR (Arnbjerg-Nielsen et al., 2015).

Despite advancements in addressing climate change, many European cities still struggle to meet the targets outlined in the Paris Agreement, underscoring the urgent need for heightened efforts to mitigate the severe impacts (Laino and Igesias, 2023). Coastal cities face significant risks from coastal storms, leading to destructive extreme sea levels, coastal flooding, and erosion. Research by Abadie et al. (2016) highlights the vulnerability of major European coastal cities like Copenhagen, Denmark. As Copenhagen facing the risks of sea level rise from all direction and the climate extreme events impact the adaptation works in the region, Denmark resort to professional' regulative and expanded institutional risk framing to be prioritise through collaborative process through influencing knowledge and innovation pathway (Madsen et al., 2019). With extensive collaboration between the knowledge companies, research institutions, and utility service providers driving in the co-production of innovative urban adaptation solutions.

Figure 8: Professionals' regulative involved in the co-production of new solutions in the urban adaptation innovation and knowledge system (Madsen et al., 2019).

In Copenhagen, the urban innovation and knowledge system for climate adaptation as depicted in Figure 8 (Madsen, 2018). Key actors include knowledge companies, research institutions, utilities, professional networks, local authorities, and citizens. These actors interact within a framework influenced by regulatory, normative, and cognitive institutions, shaping the system's dynamics (Madsen et al., 2019). Tailored each response to the necessity needs in the urban development including the implementations such as seaward development, artificial islands, land reclamation and extension.

2.4. Conceptual Framework For Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension

Figure 9: Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension in Copenhagen, Denmark. Source: Author (2024). (Adapted from Sengupta et al., 2019., Eggert et al., 2023., Gao and Zhai, 2023). With Denmark Planning System & Helix Model.

The new "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model (see Figure 9) is based on the premise of planning adaptation for coastal extension in Copenhagen, Denmark. It aims to assist planning professionals and relevant parties in making more comprehensive decisions that guide and promote the development of future-proof sustainable communities. Furthermore, it seeks to address broader objectives encompassing social, economic, environmental, and developmental aspects, as well as networks that can significantly mitigate challenges arising from climate change and introduce opportunities to wider regions.

This new conceptual framework has been developed to specifically address the decision-making process of planning adaptation across the cycle of development planning in the wider level. From recognizing the drivers, climate extreme, politics, environment, economy, and growth which are all crucial factors for decision making for coastal urban extension.

The model proposed in "Driving Forces for Seaward Urban Extension and Land Reclamation" (Sengupta et al., 2019) suffers from limitations due to its oversimplified nature, making it challenging to provide the necessary specifications for evaluating each instance of urban planning and development comprehensively. The physical landscape significantly influences the spatial configurations of artificial land construction. Utilizing remote sensing satellite imagery facilitates the identification and monitoring of these alterations, enabling the observation and categorization of construction patterns.

On the other hand, the conceptual framework outlined in the coastal vulnerability assessment (Eggert et al., 2023) has limitations regarding the criteria used to select literature sources, which may introduce bias. By exclusively focusing on documents published from 2010 onwards and written in English, the framework restricts the breadth of the assessment and could potentially overlook relevant information. This disparity could compromise the validity of the findings and weaken the overall robustness of the conceptual framework.

Although, the Cost-benefit analysis framework of adaptation planning strategies (Gao and Zhai, 2023) has limitations in the framework mentions the importance of securing funding from diverse stakeholders and seeking majority support, it does not explicitly address the challenges associated with stakeholder engagement and participatory decision-making. In complex adaptive systems like urban environments, where multiple actors with diverse interests and values are involved, effective stakeholder engagement is crucial for identifying trade-offs, building consensus, and ensuring the legitimacy and sustainability of adaptation strategies.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Questions and Objectives

The literature review identified three key elements needed to address the planning adaptation for coastal extension.

- Responsiveness and Evaluation Adaptation
- Policy Direction for Coastal Extension
- Collaborative Decision Making

There were used as the basis formulating the implementation of "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" Model aims to addressing the limitations in the existing model from responsiveness to the adaptation change, policy direction for smooth implementation, and collaborative decision-making process (see table 3).

Table 3: Research Questions.

Responsiveness and Evaluation Adaptation	Research Question 1: How could coastal extension increase the responsiveness and evaluation process to meet adaptation needed to tackle climate extreme and sea level rise?
Policy Direction for Coastal Extension	Research Question 2: How do the case studies illustrate the challenges, opportunities, and outcomes in policy direction to address the implementation for coastal extension?
Collaborative Decision Making	Research Question 3: How could the decision making process balancing the collaborative to facilitating the coastal extension in each planning level from national, regional, and municipal?

3.2. Case Studies: Lynetteholm and Holmene Development

3.2.1. Lynetteholm, New Frontier of Øresund

Figure 10: Location of Lynetteholm, between Nordhavn and Refshaleøen (left) and visual of Lynetteholm under construction (right). Source: Tredje Natur (2021).

The Lynetteholm project in Copenhagen entails the construction of an artificial island covering approximately 2.6 square kilometres, a size slightly smaller than New York City's Central Park. Envisioned as an expanse equivalent to 18 football pitches, spanning 120,000 square meters, there are plans to potentially triple its size in the future. The primary objective behind this ambitious endeavour is to safeguard the low-lying Danish capital from storm surges and the escalating threat of rising sea levels. The proposed development includes establishing a sustainable neighbourhood featuring a blend of residential and commercial properties built to rigorous sustainability standards (Carlson, 2021).

Figure 11: The proposed site of Lynetteholm, an artificial island set to be built in Copenhagen's North Harbour. The green area shows Lynetteholm's outline, the red area shows an already existing island called Refshaleøena, and the yellow an existing water treatment

In addition to providing flood protection, the project aims to accommodate housing for 35,000 residents and create employment opportunities. As part of a broader initiative to revamp Copenhagen's coastline and transportation infrastructure, efforts are underway to complete the majority of the island's foundations by 2035, with a target completion date set for 2070 (Sullivan, 2021).

Designed by COWI, Arkitema, and Tredje Natur, the 275-hectare Lynetteholm project is envisaged as a vibrant residential and business hub poised to withstand the onslaught of climate-change-induced storms. Managed by the development company By & Havn (City & Port), the construction of Lynetteholm will utilize soil sourced from various construction projects in Copenhagen and its environs, underscoring a sustainable approach to material resourcing (Tregje Natur, 2021).

3.2.2. Holmene, Denmark Green Growth Engine

Figure 12: Location of Holmene, will sit next to Avedøre (left) and visual of Lynetteholm under construction (right). Source: Guardian (2019).

Holmene, comprising nine islets, is set to become one of Northern Europe's largest and most innovative business areas, extending from Avedøre Holme in Hvidovre Municipality. The vision for this development is to recreate the original landscape shape, connecting the islets through a green nature belt. This ambitious plan aims to contribute 700,000 square meters of new urban nature and extend the coastline by 17 kilometers. Historically, Avedøre Holme boasted a rich tapestry of islands, lakes, and natural landscapes until the 1960s when it underwent transformation into a significant business hub. The success of Avedøre Holme has paved the way for the expansion represented by Holmene.

Figure 13: Visual of Holmene with its nine islets of artificial islands and floating urban extension in the South of Copenhagen. Source Urban Power (2021).

Holmene is envisioned as a 3.2 million square meter business area, emphasizing the integration of nature into its design. This approach not only provides nature experiences for the residents of the capital area but also accommodates approximately 380 new companies (Guardian, 2019). The demarcated islets facilitate the establishment of company clusters, promoting circular synergies, knowledge-sharing, and collaborative branding. Its strategic location near public transport, an international airport, and major educational institutions positions Holmene to attract companies, international investments, highly qualified employees, and foster future-proof business development in Greater Copenhagen (COWI, 2020).

The construction of Holmene as islets offers the opportunity to create an active coastline featuring running routes, dedicated biking paths, water sports facilities, and marine spots. This infrastructure is intended to engage both associations and individual athletes actively. Moreover, the proximity to the water's edge serves as a platform for nature communication, inviting families and school classes to explore and learn about the local flora and fauna (DHI, 2018).

3.3. Method

To address the research questions outlined in Section 3.1, which delve into the case studies of Lynetteholm and Holmene Development as discussed in Section 3.2, we will employ the "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model. Research Question 1 focuses on assessing the responsiveness and evaluation of adaptation strategies, particularly examining the processes involved in planning adaptation to effectively monitor and respond to climate extremes and rising sea levels.

Moving forward to Research Question 2, our aim is to highlight the challenges, opportunities, and outcomes associated with policy implementation for coastal extension. This will involve analysing policy documents at the national and EU levels to gain insights into the extent of policymakers' awareness regarding the potential impacts of their interventions in coastal extension on the respective sites and surrounding areas.

Lastly, Research Question 3 delves into the collaborative approach adopted in coastal extension projects. We will evaluate the public-private partnerships and other

stakeholder involvements at various stages of the Lynetteholm and Holmene projects to assess their effectiveness in fostering collaboration and achieving project objectives.

3.3.1. How could coastal extension increase the responsiveness and evaluation process to meet adaptation needed to tackle climate extreme and sea level rise?

Methodology: The initial step involved conducting a literature review to explore existing sustainable urban frameworks pertinent to coastal extension processes. This review encompassed frameworks such as the driving forces model proposed by Sengupta et al. (2019), the conceptual framework of coastal vulnerability assessment adapted from Eggert et al. (2023), and the cost-benefit analysis framework introduced by Gao and Zhai (2023). The objective was to gain insights into the limitations of these frameworks in elucidating the responsiveness and evaluation processes required to address climate extremes and rising sea levels effectively using Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension.

Aim: To secure improvement in the proposal of a conceptual framework that facilitates more effective adaptation for development amidst environmental and ecological changes.

3.3.2. How do the case studies illustrate the challenges, opportunities, and outcomes in policy direction to address the implementation for coastal extension?

Methodology: Data for this study was gathered from official reports of Lynetteholm and Holmene sourced from private consultancies, authorities, and national and EU parliamentary documents related to decision-making and policy direction. This included examining statements of endorsement and opposition from various stakeholders to capture a range of perspectives. Additionally, the outcomes of challenges and opportunities arising from the development were evaluated to assess the effectiveness of existing policy interventions in addressing coastal extension implementation.

Aim: The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of policy direction on seaward land reclamation projects and to understand how policy practices impact coastal extension initiatives.

3.3.3. How could the decision making process balancing the collaborative to facilitating the coastal extension in each planning level from national, regional, and municipal?

Methodology: Begin by identifying key stakeholders at various planning levels, such as government agencies, local communities, environmental organizations, and industry stakeholders. Next, it emphasizes fostering collaborative decision-making processes that engage stakeholders from all planning levels. This includes using consensus-building techniques and participatory decision-making approaches to ensure transparency, inclusivity, and shared ownership of coastal extension initiatives.

Aim: To examine the current limitations of private and public partnerships in facilitating coastal extension across different decision-making scales.

4. Findings

4.1. Responsiveness and Evaluation Adaptation

Copenhagen faces significant challenges due to projected sea level rise, with estimates suggesting an increase of 1.5 meters by 2100 according to the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS, 2020). This poses several threats, including climate protection, rising house prices, congestion, and surplus land resulting from construction (Københavns, 2020). Given these projections, it's crucial to evaluate long-term development projects like Lynetteholm and Holmene, which began construction in the 2020s but are projected for completion by 2070 and 2040, respectively, spanning 20 to 50 years.

The literature review on sustainable urban frameworks for coastal extension highlights limitations in responsiveness and evaluation of development adaptation. To address this, existing models such as the driving forces model by Sengupta et al. (2019), the coastal vulnerability assessment framework adapted from Eggert et al. (2023), and the cost-benefit analysis framework introduced by Gao and Zhai (2023) can be employed. Applying these frameworks to coastal extension strategies allows for the projection of responsiveness and evaluation processes concerning environmental, social, and economic impacts, thereby reducing uncertainty in planning proposals.

The rationale behind this approach is to ensure that development remains responsive to prospective changes over an extensive timeframe, while also enabling sufficient evaluation of external factors such as politics, stakeholders, economics, climate extremes, and sea level rise. This analysis section delves into the limitations of current frameworks and explores how the Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension model could address these challenges through more responsive and evaluative practices.

4.1.1. Lynetteholm, 50 Years Climate Protection Plan for North Copenhagen

The findings reveals both support and concerns regarding Lynetteholm's preparedness to address future development needs from 2020 to 2070. The coastal design prioritizes adaptability, employing a "process landscape" concept to create a flexible shoreline capable of being adjusted and elevated as necessary to combat rising sea levels (CNN, 2023). Environmental concerns raised by groups such as the Coalition Clean Baltic centre on potential negative impacts on the Baltic Sea ecosystem due to alterations in saline balance and marine habitats (Carlson, 2021).

Furthermore, the extensive construction timeline spanning 50 years allows for continual refinement and adaptation of design and construction methods in response to evolving requirements and emerging technologies (Københavns, 2020). However, critics caution against maladaptation, where Lynetteholm may fail to adequately address long-term climate challenges, potentially undermining its protective role for Copenhagen (Politico, 2022). By & Havn, the development company for Lynetteholm responded by altering construction plans after protests highlighted concerns that dumping excavated soil in the city's harbours could lead to water pollution and harm wildlife (Tredje Natur, 2021). To concluded, Lynetteholm is designed with foresight, emphasizing flexibility, adaptability, sustainability, and long-term integration to effectively meet Copenhagen's evolving needs

throughout construction and beyond. However, resistance from certain segments of the public underscores the importance of maintaining ongoing support and engagement throughout the project's lengthy duration.

4.1.2. Holmene, 20 Years Plan Economic Development for South Copenhagen

The findings indicate a balance of information over how the Holmene project is preparing to meet future development needs from 2020 to 2040. Primarily, Holmene aims to establish itself as a sustainable tech hub powered entirely by clean energy, incorporating a waste-to-energy plant (Urban Power, 2021). This aligns with the Danish government's commitment to achieving net-zero emissions by 2045, advancing both construction and operational practices (Danish Government, 2023).

Furthermore, Holmene is expected to catalyze job growth and economic expansion, with projections suggesting the creation of 380 new businesses and 12,000 jobs across sectors like biotech, pharmaceuticals, and life sciences (Dezeen, 2019). This economic upswing has the potential to address forthcoming regional demands and foster prosperity. However, anticipated traffic congestion resulting from increased job opportunities could strain existing infrastructure (COWI, 2019), with uncertainties surrounding the efficacy of proposed solutions such as transport upgrades.

Despite these insights, the available literature balances detailed information on strategies, plans, or design elements aimed at proactively addressing evolving future needs during the 2020-2040 period. Instead, it predominantly highlights the overarching sustainable and economic development objectives of the project, leaving room for further exploration and elaboration on its adaptive strategies and long-term planning endeavors.

4.1.3. Integration of Adaptation into the Planning Long Term Coastal Extension

Integrating adaptation into long-term planning for coastal extension is imperative for several key reasons. Firstly, projects like Lynetteholm and Holmene face significant exposure to climate change impacts such as rising sea levels and extreme weather events. By incorporating adaptation strategies during the planning phase, these projects can be engineered to endure future challenges, ensuring their sustainability over time. Showing in Table 4. To understand the practical implication over long-term coastal extension projects. By prioritizing adaptation from the outset, developers can ensure the longevity and effectiveness of their projects in the face of shifting environmental dynamics and challenges.

As projects like Lynetteholm and Holmene last over several decades, accounting for adaptation in long-term planning helps mitigate uncertainties and risks stemming from climate change. Through the evaluation of potential future scenarios and the integration of flexible design principles, developers can anticipate and respond to evolving environmental conditions, reducing the need for costly retrofits or project disruptions. The integration of adaptation fosters resilience and adaptive capacity within coastal communities. By proactively addressing climate-related risks and vulnerabilities, these projects enhance their ability to withstand and recover from adverse impacts, safeguarding infrastructure investments and the welfare of residents.

Table 4: SWOT Analysis of Sustainable Urban Frameworks for Coastal Extension

Frameworks	Strength	Weakness	Opportunity	Threat
The Driving Forces (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Provides a conceptual framework to understanding the factors influencing land reclamation. > It highlights both geophysical and anthropogenic elements, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of land reclamation. > The model can be applied to various projects, facilitating the understanding of driving forces behind seaward land expansion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The model may oversimplify the complex interactions, leading to a limited understanding of the intricacies. > It may overlook the nuanced layers of interaction, potentially neglecting crucial aspects that influence land reclamation decisions. > Due to its simplification, the model could hinder its effectiveness in informing decision-making processes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Incorporating a more nuanced understanding of the interactions between various driving factors. > The model could become a valuable tool for providing deeper insights into the factors influencing land extension initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > If relied upon in its current oversimplified form, potentially overlooking critical factors that impact the success and sustainability of such endeavors. > Failure to adequately account for the complexity of driving forces could result in inadequate planning and management strategies for coastal development.
The Coastal Vulnerability Assessment (2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Systematic methodological approach for ensuring clarity in the assessment process. > The framework outlines methodological steps, which facilitate a comprehensive analysis of coastal vulnerability. > By emphasizing the importance of sustainable urban development and climate change adaptation, the framework aligns with current environmental concerns and policy objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The eligibility criteria used may not fully capture the complexity of coastal vulnerability, potentially overlooking critical factors specific to certain contexts or regions. > The assessment may not encompass all the nuanced aspects of coastal vulnerability, leading to potential oversights in the assessment process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Opportunity to refine the eligibility criteria to ensure a more comprehensive understanding of coastal vulnerability. > The framework can be adjusted to incorporate context-specific factors that may influence coastal vulnerability, allowing for a more tailored assessment approach. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The framework's limitations in capturing the complexity of coastal vulnerability may result in an incomplete assessment, potentially leading to ineffective decision-making in coastal management and adaptation efforts. > There is a risk of misinterpreting the results, which could undermine the effectiveness of subsequent adaptation strategies.
The Cost Benefits Analysis Frameworks (2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The driving forces model provides a structured framework for analyzing adaptation planning strategies, particularly in urban planning contexts. > It considers accommodation and protection of infrastructures, highlighting the importance of comprehensive planning. > The inclusion of specific scenarios and multiple methods for calculating benefits enhances the robustness and flexibility of the analysis. > By incorporating indirect socioeconomic impacts, the model offers a holistic perspective on adaptation planning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The model may overlook certain complex interactions and feedback loops within urban systems, leading to potential oversimplification of the analysis. > It may struggle to capture the full range of uncertainties and dynamic changes associated with climate impacts and adaptation measures. > There could be limitations in accurately quantifying and valuing certain indirect socioeconomic impacts, potentially underestimating their significance in decision-making. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The driving forces model presents opportunities for further refinement and customization to specific contexts and regions. > It can serve as a valuable tool for facilitating stakeholder engagement and decision-making processes by providing a structured approach to analyzing adaptation strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Inadequate consideration of uncertainties and changing environmental conditions may undermine the effectiveness of adaptation strategies developed using the model. > Overreliance on the model without supplementing it with qualitative insights and local knowledge could lead to suboptimal decision-making. > Failure to update and adapt the model in response to new information and emerging trends may limit its relevance and applicability over time.
The Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension (2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > This holistic approach ensures that all relevant aspects are taken into account when planning coastal extensions. > The model encourages the involvement of multiple stakeholders in the decision-making process. This inclusivity can lead to more balanced and sustainable outcomes that address the needs of various parties involved. > The model addresses broader objectives, this integration allows for a more nuanced understanding of the complex challenges posed by climate change and the potential opportunities for wider regions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > This complexity could potentially hinder effective decision-making and slow down the planning process. > Gathering and analyzing this data could be time-consuming and resource-intensive. > Due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders and diverse objectives, there may be subjectivity in evaluating could introduce bias and lead to disagreements during the decision-making process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The model provides opportunities to enhance the resilience of coastal communities, could lead to more robust and sustainable development outcomes over the long term. > Encourages collaboration among stakeholders with diverse interests and perspectives, foster innovation and creativity in addressing complex planning issues and finding effective solutions. > The model supports adaptive planning approaches that can adjust to changing circumstances and uncertainties over time. This flexibility is essential for effectively managing dynamic coastal environments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Stakeholders may resist adopting new decision-making frameworks, especially if they perceive them as overly complex or burdensome. > Limited resources could hinder its effective application, particularly in contexts with competing priorities and budget constraints. > External factors such as changes in government policies, economic conditions, or public opinion could influence the effectiveness of the model.

4.2. Policy Direction for Coastal Extension

4.2.1. Lynetteholm, What's Next to New Frontier of Øresund

A key objective of the Lynetteholm project is to safeguard Copenhagen against the adverse effects of climate change, such as more frequent and intense storm surges and rising sea levels. The artificial island is designed to serve as a natural barrier and protective barrier, shielding the city's harbour and coastline from potential damage (Mørk, 2021). However, the project has encountered significant opposition and environmental concerns. Critics argue that it could have devastating consequences for the Baltic Sea ecosystem and express apprehension that the environmental impacts have not been sufficiently evaluated. Both the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (2023) and the Danish Society for Nature Conservation have raised concerns about the extensive soil transportation required for island construction.

On October 22, 2021, the Climate Movement, a Danish NGO, filed a lawsuit against the Danish Ministry of Transportation, challenging the construction of an artificial peninsula in Copenhagen Harbor. This legal action followed the passage of a bill by the Danish Parliament in June 2021 authorizing the construction of Lynetteholmen. The Ministry contends that the peninsula serves as an adaptation measure and will help protect Copenhagen from sea-level rise associated with climate change, the plaintiffs argue that the project fails to align with Danish and European climate neutrality targets.

They assert that the Ministry has violated the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Directive by not conducting a comprehensive EIA for the entire project and instead dividing it into smaller sub-projects, a practice known as "salami slicing". Additionally, they allege that the Ministry has violated the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive by not conducting an SEA (The Climate Movement v. Ministry of Transportation, 2021). The policy direction of Lynetteholm could be into addressing the environmental demands while waiting for the legal responses from the Western High Court.

4.2.2. Holmene, What's Next to Denmark Green Growth Engine

Holmene, building upon less controversial comparatively to Lynetteholm. Building on the success of the Avedøre Holme industrial area near Copenhagen, there is a growing demand for commercial plots. With land in Hvidovre Municipality fully developed, Holmene offers an extension to accommodate 380 modern logistics companies, high-tech manufacturers, warehouses, and other businesses, potentially creating 12,000 direct new jobs and up to 30,000 indirect jobs (COWI, 2019). The Holmene project is strategically positioned to receive support from the Danish Government and National Parliament, aiming to develop a new commercial district that fosters innovation and economic growth for Copenhagen and beyond (Hvidovre Kommune, 2019).

Denmark, being the European Union's largest oil producer, pledged in 2020 to cease all oil and gas exploration in the North Sea by 2050, coinciding with the EU's aim to become the world's first climate-neutral bloc by the same year (Industry Leaders, 2021). The Holmene project plays a pivotal role in Denmark's ambitious plan to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and transition to an all-renewable energy grid (World Economic Forum, 2019).

The envisioned islands will host 200-600 offshore wind turbines capable of generating 10 GW of renewable electricity, sufficient to power 3-9 million households in Denmark and neighbouring countries (Urban Power, 2021). Additionally, the project includes plans for the largest waste-to-energy plant in Northern Europe, which will convert bio-waste and wastewater from 1.5 million people into clean water and biogas (Architect's Newspaper, 2019). By integrating adaptation measures into its future plans, the project addresses sustainability, environmental concerns, and economic development needs across Copenhagen.

4.2.3. Alignment, Direction, and Leadership in Implementing Coastal Expansion

In the development of coastal expansion projects like Lynetteholm and Holmene, ensuring policy alignment, direction, and effective leadership are essential aspects. These projects face distinct challenges and opportunities that require careful consideration and strategic planning to navigate the policy in practices. For coastal extension programs to be effective, there needs to be alignment among the various stakeholders, such as government agencies, community organizations, and local residents. When everyone is working towards a common goal and vision, it creates a cohesive and coordinated effort that can lead to better outcomes. Misalignment can result in conflicting priorities, inefficient use of resources, and a lack of progress.

Coastal extension programs require clear direction and strategic priorities to guide their implementation. Leaders must establish a shared understanding of the program's objectives, the specific challenges it aims to address, and the strategies for achieving those goals. Without a clear direction, the program may lack focus, and its impact may be diluted.

Effective leadership is essential for driving the implementation of coastal extension programs. Leaders must be able to inspire and motivate stakeholders, facilitate collaboration, and make informed decisions. They must also be able to adapt to changing circumstances and overcome obstacles that may arise during the implementation process. Strong leadership can help ensure that the program remains on track and achieves its intended outcomes.

Lynetteholm, envisioned as a protective measure against climate change impacts, particularly storm surges and rising sea levels, has encountered significant opposition and environmental concerns. Critics argue that the project could have detrimental effects on the Baltic Sea ecosystem and raise questions about the adequacy of environmental impact assessments. Legal challenges further highlight the need for clear policy direction and alignment with climate neutrality targets to address environmental demands effectively.

In contrast, Holmene presents opportunities for promoting innovation, economic growth, and sustainability. Supported by the Danish government and national parliament, the project aims to develop a new commercial district with a focus on renewable energy and green technologies. This aligns with Denmark's commitment to transitioning to a climate-neutral economy by 2050. By integrating adaptation measures and renewable energy initiatives, Holmene demonstrates proactive policy leadership in addressing environmental concerns while fostering economic development.

Effective policy alignment, direction, and leadership are crucial for guiding coastal expansion projects towards sustainable and resilient outcomes, balancing environmental protection with economic growth and innovation.

4.3. Collaborative Decision Making

4.3.1. Lynetteholm, Behind the Climate Frontier

Table 5: Lynetteholm key stakeholders. Source: Tredje Natur (2021).

Client	The Danish Government and Mayors of Greater Copenhagen
Architects	COWI, Arkitema, and Tredje Natur
Consulting Engineer	By & Havn
Addition Advisors	DHI group, Arkitema, and Rambøll

At the national level, the Lynetteholm project received an endorsement from the Danish government with the parliament in 2021 through the Danish Parliament. This legislation grants extensive authority to the developer, By & Havn, and the Ministry of Transport, while bypassing certain environmental regulations and safeguards (The Climate Movement v. Ministry of Transportation, 2021). However, the project proceeded without adequate consultation with neighboring countries such as Sweden, which later raised concerns about its potential adverse effects on the Baltic Sea environment.

Regionally, there are growing apprehensions regarding the cumulative environmental consequences of not only Lynetteholm but also other coastal ventures in the Øresund and Baltic Sea region. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (2023) has highlighted this issue, emphasizing the need for comprehensive studies to assess the combined impacts of these projects. The Global Centre on Adaptation (2022) has proposed the establishment of an independent multinational marine council to oversee and manage the collective effects of all initiatives in these shared marine areas.

At the municipal level in Copenhagen, the Lynetteholm initiative is framed as a dual-purpose project aimed at providing flood protection and creating new commercial and residential spaces (Tredje Natur, 2021). However, critics contend that the project's environmental ramifications have not been adequately evaluated. They advocate for alternative approaches, such as the construction of a seawall, which could offer flood protection without posing similar ecological risks.

There is a lack of meaningful collaboration and transparency in the planning and decision-making process for the Lynetteholm project, particularly around environmental concerns at the national, regional, and municipal levels. This has led to significant opposition and uncertainty regarding the project's long-term impacts.

4.3.2. Holmene, Behind the Economic Engine

Table 6: Holmene key stakeholders. Source: Hvidovre Kommune (2019).

Client	The Danish Government and Mayors of Greater Copenhagen
Architects	Urban Power
Consulting Engineer	COWI
Addition Advisors	DHI-group, MOE, Aglaja and Rambøll

At the national level, the Danish government has supported the Holmene vision and plans to incorporate it into the overall development strategy for Greater Copenhagen. The government is playing an important role in establishing the regulatory framework and business environment to enable the Holmene project (Urban Power, 2021). Regional authorities prioritize strategic development planning by leverage tenancy, while Hvidovre Municipality engage in thorough land-use planning, drafting economic and innovation growth plan (Olesen, 2022).

Regionally, Hvidovre Municipality has been in ongoing dialogue with neighbouring municipalities, business organizations, agencies, associations, universities, investors and other stakeholders to develop the Holmene project (Hvidovre Kommune, 2019). There's an established collaborative approach across the broader Copenhagen region.

At the municipal level in Hvidovre, the Holmene project was developed through a collaborative process led by the local government. COWI (2022) conducted studies, engaged with various stakeholders, and designed the project to address the high demand for commercial space in the existing Avedøre Holme industrial area as well as environmental and economic impact to the region.

Hvidovre Municipality (2019) highlights that Holmene is intended to be self-financing, with the municipality receiving income from land sales and not requiring taxpayer funding. With this proposition suggests a collaborative approach to sharing the costs and benefits of the project. There's indications that dictate the Holmene project has involved a collaborative decision-making process across national, regional, and municipal levels, with the Danish government, Hvidovre Municipality, and various stakeholders working together to plan and implement this major coastal infrastructure development.

4.3.3. More or Less? Stakeholders in Implementing Coastal Extension

In the pursuit of implementing coastal extension projects like Lynetteholm and Holmene, the involvement of stakeholders plays a pivotal role. By understanding how collaboration unfolds within the decision-making process is vital for achieving sustainable and impactful outcomes. On a national scale, the Lynetteholm project received approval from the Danish parliament. However, the absence of consultations with neighbouring countries like Sweden has raised concerns regarding its environmental impact. In Copenhagen, critics have pointed out the inadequate evaluation of environmental consequences and proposed alternative approaches. The lack of genuine collaboration and transparency has fuelled significant opposition and uncertainty surrounding the project's long-term effects.

The support from the Danish government and the active engagement of Hvidovre Municipality highlight a collaborative approach in project development. Ongoing dialogues with neighbouring municipalities, business organizations, and other stakeholders demonstrate a collective effort to address both economic and environmental considerations.

The case studies with Lynetteholm and Holmene underscore the importance of a collaborative approach involving a range of stakeholders. Collaborative planning facilitates a comprehensive assessment of impacts and enables the formulation of robust strategies to effectively address them. Coastal expansion initiatives often entail conflicting interests among stakeholders. Additionally, collaborative approaches provide a platform for managing these conflicts constructively through dialogue, negotiation, and consensus-building.

5. Discussion

5.1. Evaluating Lynetteholm

The Lynetteholm project in Copenhagen is a highly controversial artificial island development that aims to provide storm surge protection and new housing, but has faced significant criticism from environmental groups, scientists, and local residents.

From a public engagement perspective, the project has faced strong opposition. Climate activists and environmental organizations have criticized the lack of proper environmental impact assessment and the potential negative effects on the Øresund strait's ecology (Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2023). Local residents have also expressed concerns about the project's impact on real estate prices and the creation of a socially diverse environment (Politico, 2022). There have been calls for more public input and citizen assemblies to ensure equitable outcomes.

Politically, the project has been pushed forward by the Danish government and Copenhagen's city authorities, who see it as a solution to housing shortages and traffic congestion (Tredje Natur, 2021). However, experts have argued that there are better alternatives for climate protection than Lynetteholm (Danish Society for Nature Conservation, 2023). The political agreement for the project is also heavily reliant on the construction of supporting infrastructure, raising questions about its financial viability that addressed by By & Havn through land and infrastructure sale.

From an economic standpoint, the project is intended to be self-financed through land sales, but this raises concerns about escalating real estate prices and the project becoming a simple real estate venture rather than a socially diverse development (Mørk, 2021). There are also questions about the overall cost-effectiveness of the project compared to other flood protection measures comparatively to other structure which is more effective in term of value added back to the economy.

Environmentally, the project has faced significant criticism. The environmental impact assessment has been criticized for only evaluating the initial construction phase and not the long-term effects of the island and associated infrastructure development (Climate Movement v. Ministry of Transportation, 2021). There are concerns about the project's impact on the Øresund strait's salinity and ecology, which could have far-reaching consequences for the surrounding region.

To concluded, the Lynetteholm project faces significant challenges in terms of public acceptance, political support, economic viability, and environmental sustainability. While the project aims to address important issues like flood protection and housing, the concerns raised by various stakeholders suggest that a more comprehensive and inclusive approach may be needed to ensure a truly sustainable and equitable outcome.

5.2. How could Lynetteholm improve with the "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model?

Figure 14: Areas of Improvement in Lynetteholm Project (in red zone) based on Indicators for Decision-Making for Coastal Extension Model. Source: Author (2024).

Lynetteholm, as a coastal extension project, stands to gain considerable advantages from implementing the "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model. This model provides a systematic framework for comprehending the multifaceted factors influencing land reclamation and coastal development, thus furnishing invaluable insights for refining the planning and implementation processes.

First, the accommodation and protection strategies present contradictions in their objectives. While the plan aims to provide storm surge protection and address sea-level rise, it also includes residential development, creating conflicting goals. Additionally, the chosen protection measures, such as artificial islands, differ from commonly used methods like groynes and offshore breakwaters in the region. This lack of alignment suggests a need for a more coherent and well-thought-out strategy. Otherwise, it would create contradiction for the public engagement to perceive the development incorrectly. The rationality of the development project communication has a certain limitation that create a backlash from various stakeholders. These implications leading to a limited understanding that implementing over the strategies that could not create impacts that the development has planned out.

Second, there are concerns regarding the anticipated impact after the implementation of these strategies. Issues such as transportation, property values, and climate protection seem to conflict, potentially leading to negative long-term effects with limited benefits for the surrounding area. This indicates a necessity for a more thorough assessment of the project's repercussions on various aspects of the region's development. Lynetteholm with unclear of direction of the objectives leading to unclear of outcome, with project planning that failed to adequately be addressed the benefits of the project. It is natural to the developer to discuss the add-value of the development, as if there's no value added the likeliness of the project to be success is slim. Lynetteholm is facing that concern of its

capacity to not be able to deliver the added-value that it promises when proposed and approved by the Danish parliament.

Third, engagement with key stakeholders appears inadequate. The absence of involvement from research institutions or independent assessors raises questions about the transparency and thoroughness of the project evaluation process. Relying solely on private consultancy firms for assessment may introduce biases and limit the scope of the evaluation. Collaborating with environmental agencies and third-party assessors could streamline processes and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the project's environmental impact and overall feasibility.

5.3. Evaluating Holmene

The Holmene project, which involves the development of an artificial island off the coast of Denmark, requires careful consideration of various perspectives to ensure its viability and throughout implementation across the next 20 years.

From a public engagement standpoint, the project has involved sufficient extensive consultation with local communities, environmental groups, and other stakeholders to understand their concerns and incorporate their feedback into the planning process in early stage of the development (COWI, 2022). The emergent and responsive nature of public engagement means that new collectives may arise that reframe the problems and solutions in novel ways.

Politically, the project must align with national and regional sustainability goals and policies. Mission-oriented research and public engagement can help build consensus and set attractive goals for the project (Olesen, 2022). Innovation and Economic growth plan play a central role in Holmene channelling the governmental authorities with private sectors.

Economically, the project should be evaluated for its wider economic impacts, such as agglomeration effects, productivity gains, and labor market effects, in addition to the direct costs and benefits (Urban Power, 2021). Rigorous cost-benefit analysis and collaborative planning with stakeholders can help assess the economic viability of the project.

Environmentally, the project must be designed and implemented in a way that minimizes its impact on the local ecosystem and contributes to the transition to more sustainable energy systems. Community-based enterprises and grassroots innovations can play a crucial role in this regard (Guardian, 2019). Holmene is a more balance project compare to its relative like Lynetteholm that has been approved by the parliament around the same time over the environmental and ecological plan from before, during, and after construction.

5.4. How could Holmene improve with the "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model?

Figure 15: Areas of Improvement in Holmene Project (in red zone) based on Indicators for Decision-Making for Coastal Extension Model. Source: Author (2024).

Holmene, as a major coastal extension project, can significantly benefit from the implementation of the "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model. By offering a structured approach to understanding the various factors influencing land reclamation and coastal development, thereby providing valuable insights for improving the monitoring and expanding processes.

First, Holmene could enhance its approach is through a more responsive and thorough monitoring feedback process in the long term. By incorporating indicators for monitoring environmental impacts, economic performance, and social aspects, Holmene can ensure that its development remains aligned with sustainability goals and industry needs over time. This continuous monitoring will enable Holmene to adapt its strategies and interventions as needed, fostering resilience and long-term success without interrupting current proposal.

Second, the model can guide Holmene in developing a comprehensive Regional Growth & Development Strategy. By considering factors such as regional economic dynamics, demographic trends, and infrastructure requirements, Holmene can better integrate its development plans with broader regional goals and priorities especially the Copenhagen's Five Finger Plan. This alignment could enhance the project's overall impact and contribute to sustainable regional growth and development.

Third, Holmene can leverage the model to identify and leverage growth drivers effectively. By analysing key drivers such as innovation clusters, transportation networks, and investment opportunities, Holmene can capitalize on synergies and maximize the project's economic and social benefits. This strategic approach will help attract investment, stimulate job creation, and foster a vibrant and dynamic urban environment.

6. Conclusion

In the past few years, Denmark has pioneered major scale of seaward urban extension that going to be several decades long until the completion of the development. Integrating adaptation into long-term planning for coastal extension is crucial for ensuring the resilience and sustainability of projects like Lynetteholm and Holmene. By incorporating adaptation strategies early on, developers can design projects to withstand future challenges, ensuring their effectiveness over time. Enhancing their ability to withstand and recover from adverse impacts, ultimately safeguarding infrastructure investments and the well-being of residents.

In implementing coastal extension projects like Lynetteholm and Holmene, stakeholder involvement is key for achieving sustainable outcomes. Understanding collaboration in decision-making processes is crucial. While Lynetteholm gained national approval, the lack of consultation with neighbouring countries like Sweden raised environmental concerns. In Copenhagen, criticism arose over inadequate environmental evaluation and proposed alternatives, leading to opposition. However, the support from the Danish government and active engagement from Hvidovre Municipality exemplify collaborative development efforts. These case studies emphasize the importance of collaboration in addressing diverse impacts and managing conflicts constructively, ensuring effective coastal expansion planning.

The "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model proves to be a valuable tool for evaluating the Lynetteholm and Holmene projects. Through its structured approach, this model offers a comprehensive assessment of the projects' theoretical frameworks, addressing risks and opportunities in maritime urban planning for seaward development.

For the Lynetteholm project, the model enables a critical examination of accommodation and protection strategies, ensuring alignment with project objectives and identifying potential contradictions. It also facilitates an evaluation of anticipated impacts, including considerations of transportation, property values, and climate protection, thereby providing insights into potential conflicts and long-term effects. Additionally, the model assesses stakeholder engagement to ensure transparency and thoroughness in decision-making processes. Similarly, for the Holmene project, the model enhances monitoring and expansion processes by establishing responsive feedback mechanisms. It guides the development of a comprehensive Regional Growth & Development Strategy, aligning the project with broader regional goals and leveraging growth drivers effectively.

Overall, the application of the "Indicators for Decision-Making for Planning Adaptation for Coastal Extension" model empowers stakeholders with valuable insights, facilitating informed decision-making and fostering sustainable and resilient coastal development. Through its systematic approach, this model contributes to the realization of projects that not only address immediate needs but also promote long-term prosperity and environmental stewardship.

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